

DIAMAS

Developing Institutional Open Access
Publishing Models to Advance
Scholarly Communication

D7.1 Website, Communications Kit, and Social Media Presence

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Document Overview

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Executive Summary

In the transition towards Open Access (OA), institutional publishing is challenged by fragmentation and varying service quality, visibility, and sustainability. To address this issue, DIAMAS gathers 23 organisations from 12 European countries, well-versed in OA academic publishing and scholarly communication. The project will: 1. Map the current landscape of Institutional Publishing Service Providers (IPSPs) in 25 countries of the ERA with special attention for IPSPs that do not charge fees for publishing or reading. This will yield a taxonomy of IPSPs and an IPSP landscape report, a basis for the rest of the project. 2. Coordinate and improve the efficiency and quality of IPSPs by developing a European Quality Standard for Institutional Publishing (EQSIP). This quality seal will professionalize, strengthen and reduce the fragmentation of institutional publishing in Europe. EQSIP will serve as a benchmark for a gap analysis of the data.

This report provides an overview of the DIAMAS project website, brand identity, and accompanying communication channels. This includes the project logo, colour scheme, and font style, covered in the first section on the DIAMAS Visual Identity. Following this, the document gives an overview of the presentation and future dissemination materials. The document then looks at the project's online presence, with the website and supporting social media channels. The Dissemination, Outreach, Engagement, and Exploitation Plan (D7.2) will be published in month 6 and will give further detail on how each communication channel will be utilised. In addition, this report will also provide a broader overview for the project's strategy for dissemination and engagement, supported with the materials presented here. As well as the items described in this document, the project will consistently abide by the European Union's visual guidelines for HORIZON projects.

1. Visual Identity

The DIAMAS project has an original logo to give the project a clear and recognisable visual identity. This logo was selected in consultation with the project consortium at the Kick-Off meeting (Zadar, 09/2022). Three different options were put to the project partners and a winning design was selected. The most popular logo was returned to the designer and the group's feedback was incorporated.

Figure 1: Example of DIAMAS project logos in three different styles, transparent backgrounds and using the project colours

The logo comes in various versions, utilising the project abbreviation and full title, in different combinations with the project colours (as shown above). The colours used in the logo are orange (#FCB316) and blue (#385CA9). In making this choice, the accessibility of persons with visual impairments was considered. A collection of 16 variations of the logo is available on a shared drive for the consortium to access.

For project communications, Barlow Family font style will be used for all text. Consistent typography across the project website, reports and deliverables, printed materials, presentations, and other outreach activities aims to create a clear and consistent visual identity for the project.

2. Presentation and Dissemination Material

A presentation template, incorporating the above elements (fonts, logos, colours), has been created for use by the consortium for any dissemination purposes. We expect that this template will be used for all presentations given at DIAMAS events or events that present DIAMAS. The template can be edited to create presentations which match the project's visual identity, ensuring outreach conveys a consistent DIAMAS brand. The presentation template is available on the project shared drive for anyone to access.

Figure 2: DIAMAS project presentation, example of three slides

In future, materials such as posters, flyers, and leaflets will be produced to share information about the project. These items will be developed according to the needs of specific events and partners going forward.

3. Website and Common Access Point

The DIAMAS project [website](#) will act as a central point of information for the project. Here news items and events will be posted, and visitors will be able to view information about the project (scope, duration, aims) and the consortium. The menu bar on the website allows visitors the following options: about, consortium, results, news and events, and contact. In addition, it will direct visitors to the project's social media and have a sign-up page for the newsletter. Once reports are published they will be featured on the website in summary (with full versions on [Zenodo](#)). The website is branded with project colours, logos, and fonts to ensure consistency with the overall visual identity.

Welcome to the DIAMAS Project

In the transition towards Open Access (OA), institutional publishing is challenged by fragmentation and varying service quality, visibility, and sustainability. To address this issue, DIAMAS gathers 23 organisations from 12 European countries, well-versed in OA academic publishing and scholarly communication. The project will:

1. Map the current landscape of Institutional Publishing Service Providers (IPSPs) in 25 countries of the ERA with special attention for IPSPs that do not charge fees for publishing or reading. This will yield a taxonomy of IPSPs and an IPSP landscape report, a basis for the rest of the project.
2. Coordinate and improve the efficiency and quality of IPSPs by developing a European Quality Standard for Institutional Publishing (EQSIP). This quality seal will professionalize, strengthen and reduce the fragmentation of institutional publishing in Europe. EQSIP will serve as a benchmark for a gap analysis of the data. Buy-in and capacity-building is ensured by co-creation with the relevant IPSP communities of practice, creating a Common Access Point for IPSPs, an IPSP registry with 80% of IPSPs in the ERA, publishing guidelines, training materials, self-assessment tools, financial models, and shared cost frameworks. DIAMAS embraces diversity, equity, and inclusion by addressing gender equity in OA publishing OA publishing and multilingualism in 15 European languages. Special attention is paid to building and enabling the financial sustainability of IPSPs.
3. Formulate community-led, actionable recommendations and strategies for institutional leaders, funders/sponsors/donors, and policymakers in the European Research Area (ERA). Workshops and targeted networking actions will reach and engage institutional decision-makers.

In 36 months, DIAMAS will deliver an aligned, high-quality, and sustainable institutional OA scholarly publication ecosystem for the ERA, setting a new standard for OA publishing, shared and co-designed with all stakeholders.

Figure 3: DIAMAS website homepage

The project's Common Access Point (CAP) will be developed throughout the project. As this is a key output, it was decided collectively that this online component would be co-created with the insights of partners and DIAMAS outputs, being delivered in the project's final year. Once the common access point is live, the project website (relevant information only) will be migrated and integrated into the CAP.

3.2 Website Update & Milestone 6 (November 2023)

Following the European Commission's feedback, we plan to implement several changes on the DIAMAS website. These changes aim to:

1. Highlight the diversity of partners within the DIAMAS consortium, showcasing their various expertise areas.
2. Showcase the project deliverables in a more accessible manner, explaining how each contributes to DIAMAS' overall objectives.
3. Improve alignment with the IPSP audience.

However, the initial change doesn't directly address these goals; instead, it focuses on the International Advisory Board landing page and the list of board members. Currently, the board members are introduced in an ordered list. We intend to rearrange this list into a table format, making clear their affiliations—whether they belong to DIAMAS or Craft-OA.

To provide more precise details about our partners, we will augment each partner's landing page with a paragraph describing their role and involvement in work package(s) in their respective page description under the Consortium menu bar sub-section.

To emphasise the project's deliverables, we plan a complete overhaul of the Results menu bar sub-section. Presently, deliverables are listed by their administrative names according to the grant agreement, featuring only those published on the EC portal. This layout might be challenging to comprehend for someone external to the project or unfamiliar with EU projects, potentially leading to quick bounce. With the proposed structure, we maintain compliance with the grant agreement and its terminologies while taking a more educational approach. Rather than a simple table as the main landing page, we will include explanatory content about DIAMAS' expected deliverables, their timelines, purposes, and how they interconnect. Hyperlinks from landing pages detailing work package activities will be incorporated within this main landing page, illustrating the coherence of project activities. Consequently, we will create new landing pages for each work package. This approach streamlines information by detailing work package objectives and listing deliverables, submitted or not, in chronological order to understand the rationale behind every activity. This will include details such as involved institutions, deadlines, and Zenodo links. Lastly, the original landing page featuring all submitted deliverables will be retained at the bottom of the scrolling menu. This page offers an overview of the current DIAMAS' achievements, which is easier to understand with all the new information.

These changes are planned for implementation by February 2024, aligning with DIAMAS' Milestone 6 Website, Communication Kit, and Social Media Presence Iteration 1.

The project website was initially designed in a basic manner to reduce costs for CAP, as indicated above. An addendum will be necessary to integrate the current website into the future CAP (as originally discussed in Section 3)

4. Social Media Presence

To disseminate and inform our audience about DIAMAS, several social media channels have been established to give the project a significant online presence. The project has a dedicated [Twitter](#), [LinkedIn](#), and [YouTube](#) page. All are updated with the relevant project logos for consistency across the project to build the DIAMAS visual identity. Full details of how the channels will be used will be stated in D7.2 (month 6).

5. Summary

The DIAMAS project's Website, Communications Kit, and Social Media Presence, as presented in this deliverable, provides an overview of the project's identity and its external channels and means of communication. At present, this is achieved through social media channels, a presentation template, and a website as a central point of information, all with consistent and recognisable logos, colour schemes, and font. The clear and strong DIAMAS project identity will be paired with outreach efforts to maintain a recognisable brand that stakeholders will identify and engage with across the project's duration.

Information and dissemination work will follow the visual guidelines outlined here. For example, posters, leaflets, and printed materials will follow these guidelines. Additional materials, such as leaflets, posters and presentations, will be created on an ad hoc basis, according to the brief.

As mentioned in the introduction, this document will be supported by Deliverable 7.2, which will outline how the project will use the above elements in project communication, dissemination, and engagement activities.

Consortium Overview

AMU	UNIVERSITÉ D'AIX MARSEILLE	FR
PVM	PROTISVALOR MEDITERRANEE SAS	FR
OPERAS	OPEN ACCESS IN THE EUROPEAN RESEARCH AREA THROUGH SCHOLARLY COMMUNICATION	BE
CNRS	CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS	FR
EIFL	STICHTING EIFL.NET	NL
FECYT	FUNDACIÓN ESPAÑOLA PARA LA CIENCIA Y LA TECNOLOGIA, F.S.P., FECYT	ES
TSV	TIETEELLISTEN SEURAIN VALTUUSKUNNASTA	FI
LIBER	STICHTING LIBER	NL
UB	UNIVERSITAT DE BARCELONA	ES
UniZD	SVEUČILIŠTE U ZADRU	HR
FFZG	SVEUČILIŠTE U ZAGREBU FILOZOFSKI FAKULTET	HR
Science Europe	SCIENCE EUROPE	BE
EUA	ASSOCIATION EUROPÉENNE DE L'UNIVERSITÉ	BE
OASPA	STICHTING OPEN ACCESS SCHOLARLY PUBLISHERS ASSOCIATION	NL
UiT	UNIVERSITETET I TROMSØ - NORGES ARKTISKE UNIVERSITET	NO
CNR	CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE	IT

UGOE	GEORG-AUGUST-UNIVERSITÄT GÖTTINGEN STIFTUNG ÖFFENTLICHEN RECHTS	DE
SPE	STICHTING SPARC EUROPE	NL
UU	UNIVERSITEIT UTRECHT	NL
EKT	ETHNIKO KENTRO TEKMIRIOSIS KAI ILEKTRONIKOU PERIECHOMENOU	EL
IBL PAN	INSTYTUT BADAŃ LITERACKICH POLSKIEJ AKADEMII NAUK	PL
ESF	FONDATION EUROPÉENNE DE LA SCIENCE	FR
JISC	JISC LBG	UK
DOAJ	INFRASTRUCTURE SERVICES FOR OPEN ACCESS C I C	UK

